

Assessing the Performance of a Proton Exchange Membrane Green Hydrogen Generation System through Stack and Balance of Plant Modeling

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The integration of Proton Exchange Membrane electrolyzers into hydrogen generation systems offers significant potential for sustainable energy solutions. Integrating hydrogen production with electricity, heat, and renewable energy sources enhances sustainability. PEM electrolyzers effectively address renewable energy intermittent by converting energy into hydrogen, leveraging their ramp rate and load-following capabilities. However, widespread commercialization hinges on cost reductions through new material development and a comprehensive understanding of the system's heat, mass, and electrochemical processes. This study presents a zero-dimension model developed using the Aspen Custom Modeler, detailing the electrochemical phenomena. A holistic PEM electrolysis model, including the stack and the Balance of Plant, is developed in Aspen Plus, demonstrating an overall system efficiency of 50%, with the BoP accounting for 8% of total electricity consumption. This research underscores the critical role of optimizing BoP subsystems and integrating grid-based backup solutions to enhance the economic viability and resilience of PEM electrolysis systems.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen and its derivatives, both low-carbon and renewable, are acknowledged as essential components in the energy transition aimed at replacing fossil fuels in decarbonizing sectors that are currently challenging to electrify, known as the "hard-to-decarbonize sectors": shipping, aviation, and certain industrial processes (1). The forecast for renewable power capacity dedicated to hydrogen and hydrogen-based fuel production by International Energy Agency indicates an increase of 45 GW between 2023 and 2028, comparable to Sweden's entire installed electricity generation capacity. This growth is primarily driven by China, followed by Saudi Arabia and the United States, which together will constitute over 75% of the renewable capacity for hydrogen production by 2028. Current business drivers focus on achieving greenhouse global gas reduction targets for 2030 and carbon-neutral targets for 2050 (2).

Recently, there has been a notable increase in hydrogen production projects aimed at energy and climate goals. Since 2000, around 230 projects have been launched globally to convert electrical energy into hydrogen for various energy and climate applications. Among these projects, both alkaline and proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers

are frequently used, with recent projects showing a preference for PEM. This trend reflects the experimental nature of many projects that explore less mature technologies with high potential for cost reduction. Additionally, solid oxide electrolyzer cells (SOECs), which offer higher efficiencies, are beginning to penetrate this market.

PEM electrolyzer systems were developed to address some operational drawbacks of alkaline electrolyzers. They utilize pure water as electrolyte, eliminating the need for recovery and recycling of the potassium hydroxide electrolyte which is required in alkaline systems. PEM electrolyzers can produce highly compressed hydrogen for decentralized production and storage at refueling stations, with pressures ranging from 30 bar to 60 bar without an additional compressor, and up to 100–200 bar in some systems, compared to 1 bar to 30 bar for alkaline electrolyzers. They offer flexible operation, including the ability to provide frequency reserve and other grid services, with an operating range from zero to 160% of design capacity. However, PEM electrolyzers require costly electrode catalysts like platinum and iridium and membrane materials, and their lifespan is currently shorter than that of alkaline electrolyzers (AELs). (3).

Zero-dimensional modeling in electrolyzers offers several advantages, primarily by reducing system complexity and enabling straightforward analysis and integration of key parameters such as temperature, pressure, and efficiency. These models provide system-level insights, including energy balance, mass flow rates, and the impact of operational strategies on overall performance. They are designed to predict the performance of the electrolyzer under steady-state conditions and to capture transient behavior during changes in operational parameters.

Many studies have investigated PEM electrolyzer modeling in zero-dimension. D.S. Falcão and Pinto (4) have published a comprehensive compilation of models focusing on key equations used to predict cell voltage in PEM electrolyzers. These models address reversible voltage, activation losses, ohmic losses, mass transport losses, dynamic behavior, two-phase flow effects, and thermal effects. Sayed-Ahmed et al. (5) compared the behavior of PEM electrolyzers under dynamic operation to reduce the levelized cost of green hydrogen. They suggest the rise of data-driven approaches, such as machine learning, to bridge the gap created by the complex interactions within the electrolyzers. Yodwong et al. (6) highlighted the importance of understanding PEM electrical characteristics for accurately simulating hydrogen production systems powered by RES. Using MATLAB, they simulated the operation of PEM electrolyzers with a focus on power electronics control, emphasizing that load modeling is critical for control purposes and system performance.

While previous research predominantly focuses on the PEM stack, only a limited number of studies delve into system-level modeling that incorporates the Balance of Plant (BoP). Majumdar et al. (7) emphasized the importance of understanding the fundamental physics and interactions between subsystems, reviewing control-oriented electrochemical, thermal, mass transport, and equivalent circuit models to identify adjustable system variables and control parameters for optimizing system operation. Stansberry and Brouwer (8) conducted an experimental dynamic dispatch of a 60-kW proton exchange membrane electrolyzer, aligning its operation with a load of rooftop solar PV output and aggregated wind farm power. Their investigation revealed that imposing a minimum load condition enhanced overall system efficiency by mitigating high parasitic losses at low power levels

and facilitating system cycling through rapid cold start-up capabilities. Furthermore, they identified the gas drying process as a significant contributor to losses during low power conditions. Crespi et al. (9) introduced a comprehensive model that integrates the PEM stack with BoP components and a control system. Their study evaluated a 60-kW electrolysis system for flexible dynamic operation, both theoretically and experimentally. They demonstrated that their model effectively accommodates partial load operation without substantial deviations in stack temperature and pressure, achieving good agreement between simulation and experimental data. Mancera (10) focused on optimizing the BoP for a medium-sized PEM electrolyzer through design and control implementation. The BoP includes subsystems for water management, hydrogen production, cooling, and control. The designed control logic, validated by experimental data, demonstrated correct operation across various operational states of the plant.

Efficiency considerations for PEM electrolysis are critical, as unrealistic expectations can lead to future cost concerns. The main reasons for energy losses in the PEM system are identified as follows: (a) inefficiencies in the stack caused by electrical resistance in the cell components, bubble formation around electrodes, and heat dissipation; (b) inefficiencies due to the electrolyzer's operational load profile, including frequent start-ups and shutdowns and (c) inefficiencies from the surrounding balance of the plant (BoP), such as gas processing technologies and compressors. Matošec (11) highlighted potential system-level improvements, emphasizing the reduction of standby and shutdown events, oversizing renewable energy sources (RES) when directly coupled, and integrating hybrid systems. Additionally, in the BoP, trade-offs between the performance of the stack and the surrounding subsystems are crucial considerations from both an efficiency and cost perspective.

Regarding utilized software, various tools have been used for the zero-dimensional modeling of PEM electrolysis systems. MATLAB-Simulink is commonly employed for dynamic control analysis, system dynamics modeling, and integrating control algorithms with real-time data. Espinosa-Lopez et al. (12), developed an electrochemical steady-state and semi-empirical submodel coupled with a lumped thermal capacitance dynamic submodel to predict the stack voltage and the stack temperature evolution from instantaneous operating conditions such as the applied current, the gas storage pressure tanks (H_2 and O_2) and the ambient temperature. However detailed thermodynamic modeling and integration of complex process units often require additional effort. AspenTech's Aspen Plus is another option, specializing in process simulation and optimization with rigorous thermodynamic models and comprehensive property databases by calculating phase equilibria, reaction kinetics, and physical properties of substances within the process. Aspen Plus models benefit from calibration against extensive thermodynamic and transport property data, and standardized models are available for various processes. Therefore, Aspen Plus models are advantageous due to their calibration against a broad range of data and the availability of standardized models for diverse process simulations (16).

Only a few papers have utilized the Aspen Package to model PEM electrolysis plants, primarily because the PEM stack is not a standardized model and must be developed in the Aspen Custom Modeler (ACM). Zaccara (13) conducted a comparative analysis of different hydrogen production processes from renewable energy using Aspen Plus V11. The developed models and simulations provided sensitivity analyses to gather valuable

information about process behavior, though the PEM stack was represented simply as a reactor. The first significant reference to PEM stack modeling in ACM was by Colbertaldo (14), who created a zero-dimensional dynamic model of PEM electrolyzers. His model, validated against available literature data, successfully reconstructed the stack behavior (14). This work was further expanded by Botsis (15), who introduced geometric considerations into the model and aimed to simulate the operation of a commercial PEM electrolyzer experimentally tested and manufactured by Proton On Site, with a nominal power of 60 kW. Finally, Aspen Technology Inc. published a guide on water electrolysis with PEM, building on the models developed in previous studies (16).

PEM coupling with renewable energy sources (RES), particularly when grid electricity is unavailable, poses challenges related to efficiency losses. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach. Power electronics present a potential solution, but a crucial preliminary step involves understanding PEM electrolysis system operations more deeply. Many existing studies predominantly focus on the PEM stack, often overlooking the Balance of Plant (BoP), despite its significant contribution to the overall investment cost. The BoP requires electricity from the power source for its operation, a factor frequently omitted from the levelized cost of hydrogen calculations. By expanding the focus beyond the PEM stack to include the BoP, we can gain valuable insights into the overall system efficiency and the impact of different electrical sources. This work aims to fill this literature gap by emphasizing the importance of the BoP in PEM electrolyzer systems. This comprehensive approach aims to pave the way for more holistic and efficient PEM electrolyzer systems, thereby advancing sustainable energy solutions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents an overview of the PEM electrolysis system considering the PEM stack and the BoP. Section 3 delves into the model description of the PEM stack, that was developed in ACM. In Section 4, the results of the Aspen Plus model are presented and important factors of the operation are calculated. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the key findings, addresses potential implications, and suggests directions for future research.

2. PEM Electrolysis System

In a PEM electrolyzer (PEMEL), an electric current drives the decomposition of water, which is fed to the anode, into hydrogen and oxygen. The occurring semi-reactions are:

The electrolyte in a PEM electrolyzer, typically a solid polymeric electrolyte such as Nafion (PSFA), facilitates the movement of charge carriers (H^+) from the anode to the cathode, where hydrogen is produced. These membranes provide high proton conductivity and low gas crossover, and their low thickness and capability to handle high current densities (up to 2 A cm^{-2}) enable a compact design. In terms of raw materials, PEMEL is particularly demanding, requiring significant amounts of titanium (Ti), platinum (Pt), and iridium (Ir). These rare metals pose potential long-term challenges for the commercial operation of PEMELs, especially for large-scale projects exceeding 100 MW. Titanium is used in components such as bipolar plates and porous transport layers (PTLs) due to its

excellent performance and stability under high potential in acidic conditions. Platinum and iridium are catalysts for the highly demanding electrocatalytic reactions in acidic media, with as of today typical loadings of around 0.3 kg/MW for Ir and 0.7 kg/MW for Pt. Additionally, platinum coats some titanium components, primarily PTLs (17). A significant advantage of PEMEL technology is its reduced requirement for balance-of-system components, as it does not need electrolyte tanks or gas separators. High-pressure PEM electrolyzers operate at pressures ranging from 1 bar to 200 bar, typically less than 35 bar in industrial settings. Operating temperatures are maintained between 50° C and 80° C. The specific electricity consumption of the stack is on average 56.3 kWh/(kg H₂). The expected lifetime of these systems ranges from 50,000 h to 75,000 h. As stack production scales up, the production cost of PEMEL is decreasing, currently ranging between 850 €/kW and 1500 €/kW, with hydrogen gas purity reaching 99.995% (18).

The most pressing technical challenges for today's PEMEL systems include achieving optimal system efficiency and ensuring safe operation based on electrical energy and cell configuration specifics. Key challenges are:

- Trade-off between efficiency and gas purity. Thinner membranes reduce specific power but lead to higher gas cross-over.
- Gas cross-over is higher at lower production rates, limiting the lower end of the operability envelope
- Bubble formation can limit the upper end of the operability envelope
- Rapid technology evolution requires new catalysts and membranes soon

Addressing these challenges is crucial for advancing PEM electrolyzer systems and enhancing their efficiency and safety in various applications (1).

2.1 Balance of the Plant

Beyond the electrolyzer stack, a hydrogen plant requires several components to deliver hydrogen to the final off-taker. This subsection introduces the components used in this study, emphasizing those identified by capital letters and parentheses in the text. These components are illustrated in the flow sheet diagram of the PEM electrolysis system in Aspen Plus. (Figure 1).

Power Electronics. Until recently, the power supply system relied on the power grid. With the build-out of more distributed energy sources, e.g., photovoltaics and wind power generation, power electronics are designed specifically for electrolyzers. PEMELs coupling with RES could be either direct or indirect coupled. Both require power electronics with many topologies to be investigated regarding the power output of the RES. Typically, each electrolyzer unit is paired with a set of power electronics, varying in size and units, inclusive of rectifiers and/or transformers. These components transform the AC to DC and rectifiers will deliver the appropriate DC required for the different stacks. Lei et al. (18) concluded in their research that the interleaved parallel inductor-inductor-capacitor (LLC) topology constructed by wideband-gap-power semiconductors and controlled by the zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) algorithm is the ideal candidate for an electrolyzer power supply. While power electronics losses significantly contribute to efficiency losses in a PEM electrolyzer (PEMEL) system, addressing these losses are not the primary focus of this work.

Nitrogen supply subsystem. Nitrogen is crucial in green hydrogen production for safety and component preservation. It is used to purge and pressurize systems, reducing the risks associated with hydrogen's flammability. Nitrogen purging before electrolysis removes residual gases, minimizes electrolyzer degradation, and ensures system safety. It also creates an inert atmosphere during maintenance and repair, while blanketing stored hydrogen for added safety. As this work focuses on steady-state hydrogen production without including maintenance considerations, the nitrogen supply subsystem is excluded from the system boundaries.

Water Treatment Plant and Water subsystem. High-purity water is necessary as an input to the electrolyzers since impurities can affect the reaction by depositing in the electrolyzers, on the electrode surfaces, and in the membrane. Water quality requirements vary across electrolyzer manufacturers, but typically deionized water is necessary, such as water Type I or II, as defined by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM). Therefore, most electrolyzers in the market thus include a deionization step as part of the equipment (19). Large volumes of water are needed for hydrogen production and therefore, water treatment plants will be coupled to hydrogen production. In general, water sources can be split into several types such as surface water, groundwater, city or drinking water, seawater or effluent, or treated wastewater. Each type needs a slightly different approach as they contain varying contents of minerals, sediments, and other contaminants. Furthermore, depending on the amount of treatment necessary, different amounts of water extracted will be necessary. For 1m^3 of ultrapure water, it will be required to source 1.4m^3 of groundwater, 1.5m^3 of wastewater or surface water, and 3.3m^3 of seawater. However, in each case, there will be a pre-treatment step followed by polishing within the water treatment. The source of water determines the pre-treatment and the polishing step is determined by the electrolyzer technology (20).

While water pre-treatment is a significant part of a PEMEL plant, it is not included within the boundaries of the examined PEMEL system in this work with Aspen Plus. Instead, only the water subsystem is considered, which includes the deionized water storage tank, the water circulation pump (A-PUMP), the water recirculation system (FSPLIT), and the water preheater (A-COOL). The deionized water tank model receives the input temperature, pressure and flow rate of the inlet water flows as well as the required flow rate of the outlet flows, resulting from the other components' balances. The feed water cooler is a counter-current plate-type heat exchanger. The flow conditions at the circulation pump outlet (pressure and temperature), as well as the electric consumption, are calculated according to a steady-state model from the flow rate, temperature, and pressure of the inlet flow, assuming constant isentropic and mechanical efficiency.

Cooling subsystem. Cooling systems are essential in green hydrogen production, particularly during the electrolysis and compression stages. They prevent damage and decrease efficiency by managing excessive heat generated by electrolysis. Efficient cooling is crucial for optimal operation and longevity of the electrolyzer system and involves coolants and heat exchangers. These cooling systems maintain components at optimal temperatures, contributing to stability, durability, and overall process efficiency. In this work cooling systems are designed in Aspen Plus with the name COOL.

Oxygen-water and hydrogen-water separators. The separators are tanks where the $\text{O}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{H}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ mixtures from the electrolyzer's anode or cathode outlets are collected and

cooled. This cooling process allows liquid water to condense and separate from oxygen or hydrogen by gravity. The gas (oxygen or hydrogen saturated with water vapor) exits from the top of the tank, while the liquid water is drained from the bottom and directed back to recirculation systems. In this setup, the O₂-H₂O separator (SEP-O₂) has an additional inlet for freshwater replenishment, with its flow rate calculated by the Aspen Plus Calculator. The water separator model calculates the flow rate and composition of hydrogen exiting the component, ensuring that all condensed water is effectively separated. Additionally, the H₂-H₂O separator (SEP-H₂) receives part of the water from the hydrogen dryer (PSA) (9).

Hydrogen purification subsystem. A stationary model of the hydrogen cooler (C-COOL) computes the amount of heat removed to cool down the humid hydrogen flow to a given temperature and the amount of water that condenses due to the lowering of temperature. The dryer-PSA column model (PSA) computes the amount of water that is removed from the hydrogen flow to reach the 99.995 % purity target, and the flow rate of dry hydrogen leaving the column. Two PSA dryers are needed, one to operate and the other to be in regeneration mode but for simplicity, in the present work, only the operated one is simulated in the model. The pressure difference is given by the difference between the pressure in the column in operation, assumed equal to the pressure in the H₂-H₂O separator (negligible pressure drops in the hydrogen cooler and the operating PSA column are assumed), and the pressure in the other column, whose value depends on whether the column is in regeneration or pressurization mode. When the column is in regeneration mode, its pressure is assumed equal to the atmospheric pressure (negligible pressure drops in the regenerating PSA column are assumed).

Hydrogen compression subsystem. Compressors play a critical role in green hydrogen plants, especially during the distribution and storage phases, but also by ensuring a pressure level required for offtake delivery. Once green hydrogen is produced via electrolysis, it is in its gaseous state and occupies a large volume. Compressors are used to increase the pressure of hydrogen gas, significantly reducing its volume, and making it more practical for storage and transport. However, it is important to notice that PEM electrolyzer technology can deliver hydrogen at pressures as high as 30 bar, which can be sufficient for many Power-to-X (PtX) applications. The compression process begins by collecting low-pressure hydrogen gas at controlled pressure using a valve (H2VALVE) from the suction side of the dryer and then reducing its volume with the compressor (COMP). This results in a pressure increase at the outlet, making the gas ready for storage in high-pressure tanks. The types of compressors used can vary, each has its advantages and challenges in terms of efficiency, reliability, and cost. One critical aspect of compressor efficiency lies in understanding the energy loss that occurs during the compression process (21). The prevalent design for hydrogen compressors involves multiple stages with interstage cooling, which allows the calculation of power loss, considering both shaft power and the energy consumed by the cooling system. Here, is represented by a single cooler (D-COOLER) for simplicity.

Plant Control system. Control systems are essential for monitoring and managing the operational processes, ensuring efficiency, safety, and reliability. These systems govern and oversee all stages of production, from water treatment use to electrolysis and hydrogen storage and transport. In the electrolysis process, control systems manage parameters such as current density, temperature, and pressure to optimize hydrogen production. For

and a compressor integrated with a heat exchanger (D-COOL) to simulate the compression subsystem, an aspect previously not addressed in existing literature.

To determine the optimal temperature and pressure for both the stack and hydrogen production simultaneously, sensitivity analysis was conducted across industrial range temperatures between 60°C and 80°C. Additionally, the cathode pressure was examined to simulate high-pressure PEM electrolyzers, which have garnered recent interest due to their ability to produce hydrogen at pressures suitable for various applications. Drawing inspiration from Hancke's work (23), Table 1 outlines the pressures of hydrogen production relevant to different applications.

Table 1 : Associated hydrogen pressure for relevant applications

Case	Pressure (bar)	Application
1	80	E-methanol, E-fuels, natural gas pipeline
2	200	Salt-cavern storage, compressed gas storage, ammonia production

Finally, the Aspen Plus model provides detailed insights into the electricity requirements of all the subsystems included in this study. Subsystems such as process cooling and gas purification primarily require heat rather than direct electricity. To account for this, the coefficient of performance (COP) is introduced to convert heat requirements to electrical needs. For simplicity, a common COP factor of 5 is used across all units.

3. Model Description

This section details the static model of an industrial-scale electrolysis stack, developed using ACM. The model represents the operational mode of a Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyzer, as depicted in *Figure 2*. This general model can be applied to any unit of the same technology and is based on the zero-dimensional mathematical modeling of PEM electrolyzer stacks by Colbertaldo et al. (14) and Botsis (15), as developed in ACM by Dave Humbird (16). The ACM model is divided into three main equation groups: the electrochemical model, the mass transfer and reaction model (mass balance), and thermal model (energy balance). More details of these equation groups are presented in subsections 3.1 -3.3.

3.1 Electrochemical model - Voltage

The operating principle of electrolysis is governed by the power relationship between current and voltage. Here, P represents the electric power input in the cell, V is the effective voltage across the electrolysis cell, and the current i is related to the molar rate of hydrogen production. To accurately model PEM devices, it's crucial to consider their specific details and imperfections, which set them apart from the simpler zero-dimensional modeling of alkaline electrolyzers. The following discussion outlines the equations defining the ACM's PEM cell. The cell voltage (V_{cell}) comprises an ideal voltage and several nonidealities or overpotentials, as detailed below in equation 1 (16).

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the PEM stack model developed in ACM

$$V_{cell} = V_{id} + \Delta V_{act} + \Delta V_{ohm} + \Delta V_{diff} \quad [1]$$

The ideal voltage depends on the reaction electrochemistry and can be calculated from the standard Gibbs free energy variation ΔG^o with pressure correction, where n is the number of moles of electrons, 2 electrons per H_2 molecule, involved in the overall reaction, α_{H_2} and α_{O_2} are the partial pressures and α_{H_2O} is the activity of water meaning the measure of its effective concentration which fed in a liquid state (16):

$$V_{id} = \frac{\Delta G^o(T_{stack}, P_{stack})}{nF} + \frac{RT_{stack}}{nF} \ln \left(\frac{\alpha_{H_2} \alpha_{O_2}^{0.5}}{\alpha_{H_2O}} \right) \quad [2]$$

The activation overpotential (ΔV_{act}) is computed for both the cathode and anode. It represents the extra voltage required to start the reactions, whose evolution is driven by kinetics:

$$\Delta V_{act,an} = \frac{RT}{\alpha_{an} nF} \ln \left(\frac{i}{i_{0,an}} \right) \quad [3]$$

$$\Delta V_{act,cat} = \frac{RT}{\alpha_{cat} nF} \ln \left(\frac{i}{i_{0,cat}} \right) \quad [4]$$

where, α_{an} and α_{cat} is the charge transfer coefficient in the anode and cathode respectively, Exchange current densities are described as $i_{0,an}$ and $i_{0,cat}$.

The ohmic overpotential (ΔV_{ohm}) arises from the resistance of the electrodes and the PEM itself.

$$\Delta V_{ohm} = (R_{electrodes} + R_{mem}) i A_{cell} \quad [5]$$

The electrode resistance is computed from resistivity and thickness values that are presented in

$$R_{electrodes} = R_{anode} + R_{cathode} = \frac{t_{an}\rho_{an}}{A_{cell}} + \frac{t_{cat}\rho_{cat}}{A_{cell}} \quad [6]$$

where t_{an} is the thickness of the anode, t_{cat} is the thickness of the cathode and ρ_{an} is the resistivity of the anode material and ρ_{cat} is the resistivity of the cathode material.

The membrane resistance (R_{mem}) is significantly larger than electrode resistance and is computed from a conductivity σ_{mem} (Ω/cm) which is estimated with the Springer model (22):

$$R_{mem} = \frac{t_{mem}}{\sigma_{mem}A_{cell}} \quad [7]$$

$$\sigma_{mem} = (0.005139\lambda - 0.00326)\exp\left(1268\left(\frac{1}{303} - \frac{1}{T_{stack}}\right)\right) \quad [8]$$

where t_{mem} is the thickness of the membrane and T_{stack} the operational temperature of the cells. It is important to note that the symbol i used in equations 3, 4, 5, and later refers to the “useful” current density not the original current density of the cell, introducing the Faraday efficiency. The Faraday efficiency is taken to be constant at $\eta_F = 0.99$ for simplification.

$$iA_{cell} = I_{stack}\eta_F = i_{cell}A_{cell}N_{cells}\eta_F \quad [9]$$

Finally, diffusion losses (ΔV_{diff}) are computed for the anode side only, using a limiting current term. Diffusion losses are orders of magnitude smaller than those computed above for this in some works are skipped.

$$\Delta V_{diff} = \frac{RT_{stack}}{\alpha_{an}nF} \ln\left(\frac{i_L}{i_L - i}\right) \quad [10]$$

where, i_L is the limited current density.

The above equations are solved simultaneously with ACM. The stack input power W_{stack} can be set to any value within the electrolyzer's capacity, as specified by the user.

$$W_{stack} = V_{cell}i_{cell}A_{cell}N_{cells} \quad [11]$$

3.2 Mass Transfer and Reaction Equations

The hydrogen production rate at the cathode depends on the electrochemical behavior of the cells. The associated consumption of water and production of hydrogen and oxygen is determined according, to the reaction stoichiometry:

$$nFN_{H_2,prod} = iA_{cell}N_{cells} \quad [12]$$

$$nFN_{O_2,prod} = 2iA_{cell}N_{cells} \quad [13]$$

Most of the water fed to the anode undergoes the oxygen evolution reaction, generating H⁺ and oxygen. The net water flow through the membrane can be described by three processes: (1) electro-osmotic drag ($N_{H_2O}^{eo}$), (2) diffusion ($N_{H_2O}^{diff}$), and (3) hydraulic pressure effects ($N_{H_2O}^p$). Although the membrane is designed primarily for proton permeation, it is not entirely impermeable to water. Water can diffuse across the membrane through these three main mechanisms, transporting also from the anode to the cathode. Thus:

$$N_{H_2O}^{mem} = N_{H_2O}^{eo} + N_{H_2O}^{diff} + N_{H_2O}^p \quad [14]$$

Water is dragged from the anode to the cathode by electro-osmotic forces (eo) formed in equation 15.

$$FN_{H_2O}^{eo} = n_d i A_{cell} N_{cells} \quad [15]$$

where the coefficient n_d can be assumed constant or dependent on membrane humidification as follows:

$$n_d = 0.0029\lambda^2 + 0.05\lambda - 3.4 \times 10^{-19} \quad [16]$$

Diffusion of water losses is small again because the difference in water concentration across the membrane is practically negligible. In ACM, the water concentrations are computed with the help of Aspen Properties.

$$N_{H_2O}^{diff} = \frac{D_{H_2O}^{eff} (C_{H_2O,an} - C_{H_2O,cat}) A_{cell} N_{cells}}{t_{mem}} \quad [17]$$

The effective diffusivity $D_{H_2O}^{eff}$ is determined from the temperature-dependent diffusivity (D_{H_2O}) and the porosity ε , as described in equation 18.

$$D_{H_2O}^{eff} = D_{H_2O} \varepsilon^{1.5} = 1.25 \times 10^{-6} \exp \left[2416 \left(\frac{1}{T_{amb}} - \frac{1}{T_{stack}} \right) \right] \varepsilon^{1.5} \quad [18]$$

The cathode side generally operates at a higher pressure than the anode. Pressure-driven crossflow across the membrane offsets the electro-osmotic losses. Density and viscosity on the cathode side are computed with Aspen Properties. Hydraulic pressure effects are described by equation 19, where K_{Darcy} is the membrane permeability to water. The minus symbol shows that the positive flow is from the anode to the cathode.

$$N_{H_2O}^p K_{Darcy} A_{cell} = \frac{-\rho_{H_2O} (P_{cat} - P_{an})}{\mu_{H_2O} t_{mem}} \quad [19]$$

The mass balance is derived from the production of H₂ and O₂ at the cathode and anode, respectively, the loss of water due to electrolysis, and the migration of water across the membrane. It considers the molar flow rates of hydrogen ($N_{H_2,cat,out}$), oxygen

($N_{O_2,an,out}$), and water at both electrodes ($N_{H_2O,cat,out}$ and $N_{H_2O,an,out}$). This mass balance is formulated without incorporating a storage term, which would require detailed information about the channel geometry—beyond the scope of this preliminary work. Therefore, it is expressed on a molar basis as follows:

$$N_{H_2,cat,out} = N_{H_2,cat,in} + N_{H_2,prod} \quad [20]$$

$$N_{O_2,an,out} = N_{O_2,an,in} + N_{O_2,prod} \quad [21]$$

$$N_{H_2O,cat,out} = N_{H_2O,cat,in} + N_{H_2O}^{eo} + N_{H_2O}^{diff} \quad [22]$$

$$N_{H_2O,an,out} = N_{H_2O,an,in} - N_{H_2O}^{eo} - N_{H_2O}^{diff} - N_{H_2O}^p \quad [23]$$

3.3 Thermal model equations

Water splitting in a nonspontaneous endothermic reaction requires energy to occur, which is fed to the system in the form of electric energy (W_{stack}). The energy balance assumes that all material leaving from both the cathode and anode are at a common operating temperature T_{stack} . The stack is assumed to operate adiabatically apart from minor losses of heat due to free convection of ambient air. The overall energy balance of the PEM stack is:

$$C_{tot} \frac{dT}{dt} = H_{in} - H_{out} - Q_{loss} + W_{stack} \quad [24]$$

C_{tot} is the system's total thermal capacity and H_{in} , H_{out} the heat entering and leaving the stack. The quantity Q_{loss} is the thermal power exchanged between the external wall of the stack case and the ambient air. It can be evaluated using the heat transfer equation 25:

$$Q_{loss} = hA_{ext}(T_{stack} - 10 - T_{amb}) \quad [25]$$

In addition, the heat transfer coefficient is estimated as:

$$h = 1.37 \left(\frac{T_{stack} - T_{amb}}{L} \right)^{1.4} \quad [26]$$

The exterior surface temperature is assumed to be 10°C below the operating temperature of the stack. The characteristic length L is taken as the square root of A_{cell} . The exterior area available for the heat transfer is specified according to the configuration and physical dimensions of the stack. To generalize the exterior area, it has been scaled to the cell area with a factor of 0.22.

$$A_{ext} = 0.22A_{cell}N_{cell} \quad [27]$$

The semi-empirical equation used, along with the simplifications in certain factors, arises from the exclusion of cell geometry considerations in this work and the zero-dimensional nature of the mathematical modeling. Nevertheless, all these aspects adhere to established literature.

3.4 Model Inputs

The physical properties of the membrane, constant parameters of the cell, and operating values are sourced from the AspenTech report (15). However, the model inputs, as illustrated in Figure 2, can be freely adjusted by the user in Aspen Plus to simulate and validate an existing PEM electrolyzer stack available on the market. In Table 2 the most important parameters and model inputs of this work are gathered and presented.

Table 2 : List of Parameters that used in the ACM model

Constant Parameters	Value	Model Inputs-Parameters	Value
α_{an}	0.5	T_{stack}	75 °C
α_{cat}	0.5	P_{an}	2.5 bar
$i_{0,an}$	$1 \times 10^{-10} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right)$	P_{cat}	32.5 bar
$i_{0,cat}$	$1 \times 10^{-3} \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right)$	A_{cell}	160 cm ²
α_{H2O}	1	N_{cells}	100
λ	22	Nominal power	75 kW
t_{mem}	127 μm	Nominal current density	1.9 A/cm ²
K_{Darcy}	$1.58 \times 10^{-18} m^2$	Nominal voltage	2.43 V
i_L	$6.2 \left(\frac{A}{cm^2}\right)$	Number of stacks	1
ε	0.3		
$\rho_{an} = \rho_{cat} = \rho_{el}$	7.5 mΩ/cm		
C_{tot}	50.1 kJ/K		

4. Results

This section presents the results derived from the Aspen Plus model and the conducted sensitivity analysis. The electrolysis cell stack (STACK) operates in a steady state, producing small quantities of H₂ and O₂ whose rates depend on operating temperature, pressure, and power input. In the PEM stack, most of the water circulates through the anode side, with approximately 10% circulating through the cathode side. To maintain hydration, some water is recycled to the cathode, with any excess water is returned to the anode side. During normal operation, water migrates from the anode to the cathode as described in the mass transfer model, alongside the produced hydrogen.

An essential consideration is the inlet water temperature for both the anode and cathode sides. In both cases, the maximum observed difference from the stack's operating temperature was found to be up to 10 °C for the simulation to work without issues in stack operation. This can be mitigated by increasing the recirculation rate in FSPLITS before reaching the anode and cathode.

Figure 2 shows the sensitivity analysis results on how temperature and pressure affect current density.

Figure 2: Sensitivity analysis in operation temperature and pressure

Based on the results, operating PEM electrolyzers at lower temperatures causes the polarization curve to shift upwards due to the higher voltage needed to overcome activation energy in electrochemical reactions, thereby reducing efficiency. Conversely, higher temperatures enhance reaction kinetics, improve proton conductivity, optimize water and thermal management, increase material durability, and facilitate integration with other heat-generating processes. These effects lower overpotentials and boost efficiency. A drawback of higher operation temperature is the higher heat loss in the stack and the potential crossover, for this, in this work 80°C is the maximum operation temperature, that was investigated. Regarding cathode-side operation pressure, it has the opposite effect compared to temperature. Increasing the pressure beyond approximately 30 bars has minimal impact on overpotentials, indicating diminishing efficiency returns in high-pressure PEMEL systems beyond this point.

Striving to align with industrial practices while optimizing conditions for the proposed PEM stack, it was decided to operate it at 75°C and 32.5 bars cathode pressure, both widely adopted in the industry. Table 3, summarize the results of the Aspen Plus model in the proposed conditions in steady-state operation.

Table 3: Results of the Aspen Plus PEM system model

Flowsheet Results	Value	Flowsheet Results	Value
Stack temperature	75 °C	Net generation rate before purification	1.08 kg /h
Stack power	63 kW	Net generation rate after purification	1 kg H ₂ /h
System power	69 kW	Net generation pressure	32.5 bars
Pressure (cathode/anode)	32.5 bar / 2.5 bar	Circulation rate on the anode side	1 920 kg/h
Stack losses	82.1 W	Circulation rate on the cathode side	192 kg/h
Net oxygen generation	8.72 kg O ₂ /h	Deionized water required	9.86 kg/h
PEM stack efficiency (LHV)	60%	PEM system efficiency (LHV)	50%

Determining the operating conditions for the PEMEL system requires evaluating the performance of the PEM model and verifying the accuracy of the simulation through the polarization curve, which represents the relationship between current density and voltage. The proposed simulation's ability to calculate each overpotential separately is advantageous, allowing for comparison with theoretical expectations. In a PEM electrolyzer polarization curve in *Figure 3*, the overpotential with the greatest impact on current density is the activation overpotentials at both the cathode and anode, as well as the ohmic overpotential. Other overpotentials remain relatively stable.

Figure 3: Polarization curve of the proposed PEM cell

Before proceeding to evaluate the BoP performance, it is essential to examine the specific work and efficiency of the PEM stack at different current densities. Specific work refers to the electrical energy required to produce 1 kg of hydrogen. This metric and efficiency at various current densities provide a comprehensive understanding of the stack's

operational performance. *Figure 4* illustrates these relationships, offering insights into how the PEM stack performs under different operating conditions.

Figure 4: a) Electric power input vs H₂ production and b) specific work at different current densities

A summary of the electricity consumption for all subsystems is presented in *Figure 4a*. Additionally, *Figure 4b* shows the total power consumption and losses of the Balance of Plant (BoP) compared to the stack. The analysis reveals that the BoP accounts for 8% of the total power consumption, which is consistent with values reported in the literature.

Figure 5: a) Comparison of Electricity Consumption Across Different Subsystems in the PEM Electrolysis System and b) Percentage Distribution of Power Consumption in the PEM Electrolysis System: Separating Stack and Balance of Plant (BoP)

5. Conclusions

This study presents an Aspen Plus model of a PEM electrolysis system encompassing both the PEM electrolyzer stack and crucial subsystems (BoP). Significant emphasis was placed on the representation of water, gas purification, process cooling, and compression subsystems, while subsystems such as water pre-treatment, power electronics, and control

were intentionally excluded from this analysis. The steady-state simulation of the PEM electrolysis system was successfully achieved using the ACM integrated within Aspen Plus. A zero-dimensional mathematical model sourced from existing literature was adapted for the PEM electrolyzer within ACM and subsequently integrated into the comprehensive Aspen Plus model with improvements in BoP subsystems. Standard Aspen Plus models were employed to characterize the subsystems of the plant, and system mass and energy balances were rigorously validated.

Central to this project was not only the accurate reproduction of operation process PEM electrolysis system model but also a detailed understanding of the electricity demands of the BoP subsystems. Gas separators, PSA dyers, and compressors exhibit slower ramp rates compared to the PEM electrolyzer, in a ratio of minutes compared to seconds which is the ramp rate of the PEMEL stack, underscoring the critical need to comprehend their electricity requirements, especially in scenarios where the PEM electrolysis system is coupled with RES. Frequent shutdowns can severely impact the dynamic operation of the PEM system, as the BoP units, such as compressors, gas separators, cooling systems, and water purification units, are designed for stable operation. Frequent start-up and shutdown of BoP units reduce efficiency and introduce higher maintenance costs, affecting the levelized cost of hydrogen. As indicated by our Aspen Plus model, BoP subsystems account for approximately 8% of the total electricity demand for a system producing 1 kg H₂/h. This finding highlights a significant consideration: PEM electrolysis systems, particularly those requiring intensive compression and purification, are not typically exclusively reliant on RES, e.g., off-grid design, in a steady-state operation. Reliance on RES means the plant may frequently start up and shut down based on electricity power availability. Utilizing grid backup to provide a stable electricity supply during periods without RES offers an additional advantage by enabling the electrolysis system to participate in grid balancing activities. The BoP subsystems represent a substantial portion of the operational costs of the plant, underscoring the importance of optimizing their operation, and maintenance and exploring synergies with grid-based backup solutions to enhance overall system resilience and economic viability.

Future work will involve dynamically simulating the PEM electrolysis (PEMEL) system in Aspen Plus Dynamics, with controllers added to emulate control subsystems. These controllers will regulate temperature, pressure, and power, which are critical for maintaining system stability under varying electrical inputs. Although these variations do not affect the steady-state solution, they do impact the time required to achieve stable conditions. Additionally, future research will focus on energy storage solutions essential for maintaining steady-state operations without a stable power supply. Batteries can provide short-term storage, while hydrogen storage can manage longer-term energy shifts, buffering fluctuations in renewable energy sources (RES). Concurrently, an optimization model aimed at minimizing the frequency of standby, start-up, and shutdown states will be a valid addition to the importance of system-level efficiency. Finally, incorporating a detailed description of the internal geometry will allow for a more accurate reconstruction of mass dynamics, thereby enhancing overall model fidelity.

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Credit authorship contribution statement

D. Almpantis: Methodology, Software, Writing - Original draft preparation, Visualization.

H. Davidsson: Methodology, Data curation, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision.

M. Andersson: Conceptualization of the study, Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision

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Graphical Abstract

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of a Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolysis system, focusing on the modeling of the PEM stack using Aspen Custom Modeler, alongside the essential equipment comprising the Balance of Plant (BoP).

Author Biographies

Diamantis Almpantis is a PhD candidate at the Department of Energy Sciences at Lund University, specializing in the development of comprehensive energy system models and sector coupling and also actively involved in a European project, Circular Fuels, aimed at optimizing the coupling efficiency between photovoltaic systems and electrolyzers. He holds an MSc in Sustainable Energy with a concentration on energy system analysis and an MSc in Chemical Engineering. His research interests include the modeling and simulation of large-scale energy systems, with a strong focus on hydrogen clusters.

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Martin Andersson is a Professor at the department of Energy Sciences, where his main research is on modelling of fuel cells and electrolyzer at various length scales. Andersson has a M. Sc. in Environmental Engineering from Lund University (2007) and a PhD in Heat Transfer from Lund University (2011). Martin was granted a Marie Curie Fellowship in 2015, which enabled him to work as a Guest Professor at the research centre Jülich in Germany between 2015 and 2019. Martin has served as Adjunct Professor at University of Electronic Science and Engineering of China (UESTC) in Chengdu, China since 2017. Martin is also the founder and director of the Lund University master's programme in Sustainable Energy Engineering.